

Formulation and Evaluation of Face Wash by Using Goat Milk and Honey

Nilesh Hingawe¹, Tanushree Malode², Atreyee s. mamidwar³, Dr. A. N. Maliye⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Sonekar College of Pharmacy, Koradi, Nagpur, Maharashtra India-441111

ABSTRACT

Cosmetics are the substances that are applied on the skin, face, and hair for cleansing, beautifying, and promoting attractiveness. In this research work Goat milk and honey were used to prepare face wash. The main objective of this research work was to prepare a face wash having properties like a gentle cleanser, is rich in nutrient, improve dry skin, a natural exfoliant, support a healthy skin microbiome, prevent acne, act as a pore cleanser, lightened scars and useful in sunburns. The facewash formulation is prepared by using goat milk, honey, vitamin E, and Olive oil. Carbopol 940 was used as a gelling agent. The formulated face wash was analyzed for consistency, spreadability, washability, foamability, viscosity, odor, and color. The instant multipurpose facewash can be applied to the skin and it was found to be very effective. The present study revealed that formulated facewash produced excellent foam; It is a user-friendly product that is safer for use.

Keywords: Facewash, Goatmilk, Honey, Cosmetics, Exfoliant

INTRODUCTION

Facewash is a product that is used to cleanse the face without drying it out. The face wash is also commonly called a cleanser. Face wash products are found to be equally good for all skin types. The Goat milk and Honey Face wash help you to achieve clear and flawless skin and keep it deeply nourished. It also helps in the exfoliation of dead skin. For ages, Goat milk and Honey face wash considered a blessing for the skin. This Face wash suits all skin types like Dry, Oily, Acne-prone, and even sensitive skin [1].

Skin is the most revealed part of the body which is prone to various disorders. There is a need for proper cleanliness as well as hygiene for the most exposed part of the body and prevent it from micro-organisms spreading in the environment. Thus, in preventing various skin disorders the better and more efficacious way to remove all the foreign particles is the use of simply formulated face wash with no extreme chemicals. Goat milk and honey are preferred in formulating the facewash as the active ingredient due to their wonderful properties for all skin types [2].

Forms of face wash:

1. Cream-based face wash
2. Gel-based face wash
3. Liquid-based face wash
4. Face wash in powder form

Types of face wash:

Generally, a face wash suits all skin types however now day different products are available in the market that are formulated to suit different skin types for example: an oily skin face wash is made for people who have oily skin conditions and does not contain oils and leaves a thin oily film on the skin. The different types of face washes available in the market include:

1. Oily skin face wash
2. Dry skin face wash
3. Normal skin face wash.

Feature of face wash:

1. Removing the dead cells.
2. Rejuvenating the skin cells elevated stress.
3. Removes oil, dirt, and impurities.
4. Reduces microbial flora of the skin

5. Leave skin fresh and breathing.

Gel-based face wash

A gel is a solid jelly-like material that can have properties ranging from soft and weak to hard and tough. Gels are defined as a substantially dilute cross-linked system, which exhibits no flow when in a steady state. By weight, gels are mostly liquid, yet they behave like solids due to a three-dimensional cross-linked network within the liquid. It is the crosslinking within the fluid that gives a gel its structure (hardness) and contributes to the adhesive stick(tack). In this way, gels are a dispersion of molecules of a liquid within a solid in which the solid is the continuous phase and the liquid is the discontinuous phase. The word gel was coined by 19th-century Scottish chemist Thomas Graham by clipping from gelatine [3].

Material and Method:

Material

Goat milk powder, Honey, Lavender oil, and Vitamin E were purchased from the local market. Carbapol 934, Propyl paraben, Methyl paraben, Polyethylene glycol 200, Triethanolamine, and Sodium lauryl sulfate were purchased from Loba Chemie, Mumbai.

Method

Table 1. Formulation of goat milk and honey facewash.

Ingredient	Use	F1 w/w	F2. w/w	F3 w/w
Goat milk	Exfoliate, probiotics, eczema, psoriasis	1g	2g	3g
Honey	Antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-acne.	4ml	5ml	6ml
Lavendar oil	Essential oil.	20drop	20drop	30drop
Vitamin E	Protecting and moisturising skin.	1ml	2ml	3ml
Carbopol 934	Gelling agent	1.5g	2g	2.5g
Propyl paraben	Preservative	1g	1g	1.5g

Methyl paraben	Preservative	0.5g	1g	1g
Polyethylene glycol 200	Humectant	2ml	3ml	5ml
Triethanolamine	Neutraliser	1ml	1.5ml	2ml
SLS	Foaming agent	1ml	1.5g	2ml
Distilled water	Vehicle	Q. S	Q. S	Q. S

Method of Preparation: -

1. The measured quantity of Carbopol 934 was dissolved in 50 ml distilled water and keep aside for 6 hr for complete swelling.
2. In 10 ml of distilled water in a beaker propyl paraben and methyl paraben were dissolved by heating on water bath. After cooling of solution propylene glycol and Sodium Lauryl Sulphate were added.
3. The above solution was added to water-soaked Carbopol by continuous stirring.
4. In another beaker honey and essential oil were taken and stirred until the honey was dissolved completely and turned cloudy. Then the goat milk was added with continuous stirring until the liquid blended with the mixture. This solution is then added to mixture prepared in Step 3 with continuous stirring. Distilled water was added as per requirement in the final formulation ^[3,4].

Evaluation

Determination of pH

The pH of formulations was determined using a digital pH meter. One gram of face wash was dissolved in 100 ml of demineralized water and stored for two hours. The measurements of pH of each formulation were done in triplicate. The instrument was calibrated before use with standard buffer solutions at pH 4, 7 and 9 ^[5].

Determination of Viscosity

The viscosity of the formulation was determined with Brookfield Viscometer (Spindle No. 3) at 10 rpm. 100 g of each formulation was weighed and transferred to a beaker. Samples of the

face wash were allowed to settle for over 30 min at the assay temperature before the measurements [5].

The viscosity the of formulation was determined using the formula.

Viscosity (cp) = Dial Reading × Factor

Spread ability determination of formulations

The spreadability of formulations was determined by an apparatus that was fabricated in the laboratory & used for the study. The apparatus consists of a wooden block, with a fixed glass slide with one end tied to a weight pan rolled on the pulley which was at a horizontal level with a fixed slide. An excess of whitening face wash sample 1.5 g was placed between two glass slides and a 1000 g weight was placed on the slide for 5 minutes to between compress the sample to uniform thickness weight (60g) was added to the pan. It was calculated using the formula:

$$S = ml / t$$

Where,

s = spreadability in gm. cm/sec

m= weight tied to the upper slide

l= length of glass slide

t= time in seconds

The length of glass slide was 11.2 cm and the weight tied to the upper slide was (60gm) throughout the experiment.

Washability

The product was applied on hand and was observed under running water.

Accelerated Stability Studies

The Face wash gel formulation was subjected to stability testing for 2 months as per ICH guidelines at a temperature of $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and RH 75%. The Gel formulation was analyzed for the change in appearance and pH. [6, 7].

Foamability test

In a 100 ml measuring cylinder 10 ml of face wash and 10 ml of water were shaken and the height of the foam was measured.

Grittiness

It was observed by rubbing the facewash between fingers.

Antimicrobial Testing

The antimicrobial property of face wash was tested using the pour plate method and by observing the zone of inhibition [8, 9].

In vivo evaluation

Skin irritation test

The skin irritation was carried out on human volunteers. For formulated face wash, volunteers were selected and 1.0 g of formulated face wash was applied on an area of two square inches to the back of the hand. The volunteers were observed for lesions or irritation [10].

Result and Discussion

Table 2. Evaluation parameters of face wash

SR.NO	Evaluation Parameter	F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	Creamy white	Creamy white	Creamy white
2	Odour	Lavender like	Lavender like	Lavender like
3	Viscosity(cp)	15150	23100	24100
4	Spread ability	5.36+_0.80	5.43+_1.39	5.40+_1.35
5	Washability	Good	Very Good	Good
6	Consistency	Semisolid	Semisolid	Semisolid
7	Ph	6.3	6.9	6.5
8	Foamability	Foam volume 90ml at 5min	Foam volume 100ml at5min	Foam volume 98ml at 5 min
9	Grittiness	No gritty particle	No gritty particle	No gritty particle
10	Irritancy test	No irritation	No irritation	No irritation

Accelerated Stability testing:

Table 3. Stability testing Parameters after 1 month

Formulation	Colour	Consistency	Washability	pH	Spread ability	Viscosity
F1	Creamy white	Semisolid	Good	6.30	5.601	Not change
F2	Creamy white	Semisolid	Good	6.80	5.908	Not change
F3	Creamy white	Semisolid	Good	6.50	5.410	Not change

Table 3. Stability testing Parameters after 2 Months

Formulation	Colour	Consistency	Washability	pH	Spread ability	Viscosity
F1	Creamy white	Semisolid	Good	6.40	3.501	Not change
F2	Creamy white	Semisolid	Good	6.85	5.389	Not change
F3	Creamy white	Semisolid	Good	6.50	5.409	Change

Antimicrobial Activity:

Figure 1. Antimicrobial activity of F1

Efficacy	Diameter
Before incubation	1.8cm
After incubation	3.7cm

Figure 2. Antimicrobial activity of F2

Efficacy	Diameter
Before incubation	1.9cm
After incubation	4.9cm

Figure 3. Antimicrobial activity of F3

Efficacy	Diameter
Before incubation	1.9cm
After incubation	3.8cm

Conclusion: -

Skin disease was very common and the need to prevent or treat the disease is in great demand. In the present scenario, people need remedy for skin disease without side effects. Goatmilk and honey opened the way to formulate cosmetics without harmful effect, which can impart the required properties to heal the skin disease and the expense will be less when compared with the synthetic products. This formulation can be used as an effective face wash gel. It helps to improve the skin and heal the skin disease like psoriasis, eczema. The goat milk and honey facewash also help in exfoliation of the dead skin. And work as an anti-inflammatory. The instant multipurposed facewash can be applied to skin and this facewash found to be very

effective. The present study revealed that formulated facewash produced excellent foam; It is user friendly product which is safer for the use.

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